

TADQIQOTLARDA MANBALARNI O'RGANISH: ANIQLASH, TIKLASH, TAHLIL QILISHNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola orqali manbalarni tadqiq qilishning asosiy jihatlari bo'lgan aniqlash, tiklash, tahlil qilish usullarning amaliy ahamiyati haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Manba, rasmiy hujjatlar, solnomalar, geo-kosmografik, biografik asarlar, ichki, tashqi, qo'lyozma, tadqiqot, ilmiylik, tarixiylik, xolislik, kitoblar.

Tarixiy manbani aniqlash, tanlash va nihoyat uni ilmiy tahlil qilish har qanday ilmiy tadqiqotning uning katta-kichikligidan qat'iy nazar, dastlabki bosqichi hisoblanadi. Tadqiq etmoqchi bo'lgan masalaning ilmiy hamda nazariy jihatdan to'g'ri hal etilishi ko'p jihatdan har qanday ilmiy ishning poydevorini tashkil etadigan manbaning sifat va salmog'iga, ya'ni to'laligi va faktik materialga boyligiga bog'liqdir. Yana shuni ham yodda tutish kerakki, aniq biron ilmiy masalani tadqiq etishda bir emas, balki bir necha asarga qolaversa turli tipdagi manbalar (rasmiy hujjatlar, solnomalar, geo-kosmografik va biografik asarlar)ga tayanmoq zarur.

Bularning qay biri asosiy, qaysisining yordamchi rol o'ynashi esa tadqiq etilish masalasining mavzui va harakteriga bog'liqdir. Masalan, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy masalalarini o'rganishda rasmiy hujjatlar asosiy manba rolini o'ynaydigan bo'lsa, siyosat hamda madaniy hayotni yoritib berishda solnomalar va biografik hamda adabiy asarlar birinchi o'rinda turadilar.

Lekin, shunga qaramay, ilmiy tadqiqot olib borishda faqat asosiy hisoblangan manba bilangina kifoyalaniq qolmay, ikkinchi darajali manbalarni ham bilmoq lozim. Qo'lyozma asarlar ustida olib borilgan ko'p yillik izlanishlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ba'zi tarixiy asarlar ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy masalalar hamda madaniy hayotga oid qimmatli faktik materialga ham boydir, rasmiy hujjatlar va biografik asarlar esa siyosiy tarixga oid qimmatli faktlarni, tarixiy asarlarda yo'q faktlarni uchratish mumkin. Shunday qilib, ilmiy ishda ko'p va turli tipdagi manbalarga tayanib ish ko'rish, tadqiq etilmish masalaga oid barcha manbalarni jalb etish bo'lajak ilmiy asarning qimmatini oshiradi.

Belgilangan biron-bir mavzuga tegishli manbalar tanlab olingandan keyin ularning har biri, tashqi va ichki belgilariga ko'ra ilmiy tahlil etilishi lozim.

Qadimgi qo'lyozma asarlarining yozilgan vaqti va joyini aniqlash qiyin. Ba'zi hollarda asar oxirida faqat uning ko'chirilgan vaqti va joyi kotibning ismigina qayd etiladi xolos. Bunday ma'lumotlar keltirilmagan taqdirda, asarning yozilish va ko'chirilish tarixi uning qog'ozi, xati hamda tipi va til uslubiga (stiliga) qarab taxminan belgilanadi. Asar muallifi va uning shaxsini aniqlash qo'lyozma asarini ilmiy tahlil etishda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Bu shunchaki asar muallifining shaxsinigina aniqlash uchun qilinadigan odatdagi bir ish emas, aksincha asarning yaratilish tarixi va uning yozilishiga sabab bo'lgan ijtimoiy-siyosiy muhitni aniqlab olish uchun zarurdir. Ma'lumki qadimgi qo'lyozma asarlarda ko'p hollarda muallifning ismi ma'lum va ko'zga tashlanadigan biron joyda, masalan, asarning boshi va oxirida qayd etilmaydi. Ba'zan u muqaddima qismida yoki asarning o'rtasida voqealar orasida biron masala yuzasidan tilga olinadi. Ko'p hollarda esa muallif o'zining haqiqiy ismini aytmay «faqiru haqir», «ojiz va xoksor», «bu g'arib banda» deb atash bilan kifoyalanadi. Bunday hollarda asar varaqma-varaqa, satrma-satr, zo'r e'tibor va sinchkovlik bilan o'rganilishi lozim, chunki ko'pincha shunday ham bo'ladiki, asarning biron-bir yerida muallif o'zi otasi va yaqinlari haqida bir-ikki kalima aytib o'tadi yoki bayon etiladigan voqeaga o'zining munosabatini (masalan «Abdullaxon taxtga o'tirgan vaqtida kamina Hafizi Tanish ibn Mir Muhammad 33 yoshda edim») bildiradi. Bu o'rinda yana shuni ham aytib o'tish kerakki, muallifning shaxsi, ya'ni uning qaysi ijtimoiy guruhga mansubligi, shuningdek, uning dunyoqarashini aniqlash uchun asarning umumiy g'oyaviy yo'nalishini to'g'ri belgilab olish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Manbaning tashqi belgilariga qarab tahlil etishning yana bir muhim shartlaridan biri, uning yozilish sabablarini to'g'ri aniqlashdan iboratdir. Tadqiqotchi olim qo'lidagi asarning yozilish sabablarini, qaysi ijtimoiy-siyosiy muhitning mevasi ekanligini yaxshi bilishi zarur.

Buni asarni zo'r diqqat-e'tibor bilan o'rganish orqali uddalash mumkin, xolos. Busiz asardan unda keltirilgan faktik materialdan to'g'ri foydalanib bo'lmaydi.

Manbani ichki belgilariga qarab tahlil qilish. Manbani ichki belgilariga qarab tahlil qilish deganda, uni mazmuniga qarab tahlil qilish, tushuntirish, g'oyaviy-siyosiy va ilmiy qimmatini aniqlash masalalari aniqlanadi. Har qanday asarning ilmiy qimmatini, unda bayon etilgan voqealarning, ob'ektivligi, keltirilgan faktlarning to'g'riligi, nihoyat oldinga surilgan fikr va g'oyalar bilan o'lchanadi. Shuning bilan bir qatorda bunda asarning original (asl nusxasi) yoki kompilyasiya (terma) bo'lishi, to'la va qisqaligi, voqealarning qay tarzda bayon etilishi ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi, chunki odatda ilmiy tadqiqotda original va mo'tabar nusxalariga tayanib ish olib boriladi.

Yana shunga e'tibor berish kerakki, sinfiy jamiyat sharoitida yozilgan asarlarning mualliflari ko'pincha o'zlari keltirilayotgan faktlardan to'g'ri xulosa chiqarmaydilar, ularning fikrlarida noaniqlik, chalkashlik va qarama-qarshiliklar ham uchraydi. Bu tabiiy hol, albatta, chunki ular yashab, ijod etgan muhitning o'zi ziddiyatlar bilan to'lib toshgandadir.

Manbaning mazmunini tahlil etishda yana bir narsaga e'tibor berish zarur. Muallifning dunyoqarashidan sinfiy cheklanish, voqealar va faktlar ustidan xulosa chiqarganda yuz beradigan zaruriyat va qarama-qarshiliklar bilan bir qatorda, ayrim hollarda ob'ektiv fikr yuritish hollari ham uchraydi. Bunday paytlarda muallif ko'pincha o'z fikr va mulohazalarini pardoqli iboralar va istiorali so'zlar orasiga yashiradi, shuningdek ko'p asr avval bo'lib o'tgan va aynan muallif bayon qilmoqchi bo'lgan voqeaga o'xshash faktlarni misol tariqasida keltirish yo'li bilan bayon etganlar.

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